

Nutrient Supplementations in Aquaponic Systems: A Review

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Abstract

Aquaponics is a sustainable production system which integrates fish production through aquaculture and crop production through hydroponics. It aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 2,13 and 14) of United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) to become the future farming practise to compact water shortage and environmental pollution with greater cost returns. Increased feed costs and suboptimal nutrition for plants were the major drawbacks for its global adoption. In this direction, several researches focus on manipulating fish feed and supplying external nutrient to the system. This article critically reviews existing literature published on aquaponic supplementations from past two decades. Through a systematic process, 149 most constructive papers were analysed and organized into varying groups based on content. The review found that iron, potassium and phosphorus supplementations being reported as system bottlenecks are majorly explored. Optimising fruit peel supplementation in feed is the current trend to compensate feed cost, nutrient deficiency and foster sustainable management of organic wastes. Holistically, studies on optimising feed supplementations specific to systems is the need of hour to enhance productivity and ensure socioeconomic stability in cultivation.

Keywords: Aquaculture, hydroponic, sustainable, fruit peel, feed, optimizing

I. INTRODUCTION

In the present scenario, increased climatic changes, urbanization and pandemic has posed a need for independent and multifunctional food production model by reducing the environmental consumption, labour and costs. To address the rising demand of global population for healthy aquatic foods, there is an urgent need to adopt alternative aquaculture practices that can use non-renewable resources including water, feed and energy efficiently, while reducing environmental damage and preserving natural resources. Aquatic food production is forecasted to further increase by 15 % due to expanding sustainable food practises [1]. Aquaponics is one sustainable approach to food production that combines fish production through aquaculture and plant production through hydroponics [2–4]. It is a mutually beneficial circular bio-based economical system wherein fish waste acts as a natural fertilizer for plants which in turn purify the water for its return to the fish tank. This soil-less recirculating model is widely applied across the globe as it provides high quality, safe, and nutritious food with limited use of water, labour, land and cost [5,6].

Aquaponics is a part of circular bioeconomy framework which provides sustainable solution to most environmental issues such as, limited water availability, increasing pollution, increasing fertilizer cost, arable land availability along with depleting fertile soils [4,7–9]. It uses only 10 % of water as compared to separate aquaculture and hydroponic units which need external supply of oxygen, nutrients and fertilizers. This water reuse and conservation in aquaponics is made possible by the intermediate filtration units harbouring beneficial *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrobacter* bacteria that sequentially converts fish waste containing toxic nitrogenous compounds like ammonia into nitrites and nitrates respectively for absorption by plants. Hence bacteria play essential role in the optimal development of species in aquaponics [10] Plant growth and yield are indirect linked to fish feeding strategy, fish metabolism and nitrification by bacteria. Conversely, water quality and fish growth and yield depend highly on the disposal and uptake capacity of the plant. This implies the importance of right coupling of species of fish and plant in the system.

Different aquaponic systems can be designed according to species, space and convenience. Coupled recirculating designs can independently optimize fish rearing and plant cultivation [2,3,11] with minimal water, CO₂ and energy footprint per unit of production [12,13]. On contrary to coupled systems, decoupled aquaponic do not recirculate the water back to the aquaculture tank [14] therefore being flexible in customising the aquaculture wastewater to improve nutrients utilized for plant absorption without any concerns of affecting fish. Nutrient Film - based Technique (NFT) is a system that allows a thin layer of water containing

dissolved nutrients after filtration flowing continuously through a channel to the plant roots ensuring abundant supply of oxygen to the roots. Deep water culture-based systems use floating rafts occupied by plants. Media based culture system uses bed filled with inert materials which also acts as biofilters to support plant growth.

Aquaponics has gained increasing interest in both research and practice, especially in regions facing water scarcity and food security challenges. Publications on aquaponics have increased exponentially in the past few years. This growth reflects system's commercial viability, resource efficiency, and sustainability, driven by global issues like climate change and food security [15]. Aquaponics researches align with the SDG 2 (“Zero Hunger”), SDG 13 (“Climate Action”) and SDG 14 (“Life Below Water”). This highlights aquaponics' interdisciplinary focus on environmental sustainability, food security, and public health. This review critically evaluates and highlights the published knowledge on the different nutrient supplementations in aquaponic systems so as to advance an optimised aquaponic system.

II. OPTIMIZING AQUAPONIC SYSTEM

Aquaponics provide two-way benefit to producers through fish and crop. The foundation of the system lies in a compromise between the requirements of both species. The best conditions for fishes and plants can currently be achieved through either focusing on the interdependent parameters of both system components (for example, combining fish and plant species that ideally require similar environmental conditions within the same range of temperatures and pH that ensure bacterial nitrification) or physically separating two recirculating loops, such as an aquaculture and hydroponic loop, which are known as decoupled systems. In these systems, the suitable conditions for each are facilitated by intermittent water exchange between the systems [16,17]. The choice of less impacting materials and the optimization of management practices should be regarded as a priority in order to reduce environmental impacts [18]. Optimizing quality parameters, ensuring availability of all critical growth and yield promoting nutrients, eliminating potentially toxic elements in the system such as Na, Cl, B, Fe, Mn and Al in the rhizosphere are therefore necessary to obtain maximum output. Compatibility between fish, plant and production type is also important [5,19,20]. Several authors have reported on various factors needed for optimum production in aquaponics systems [21,22]. Some of the major factors as depicted (in figure 1) are discussed below.

Figure 1. Overview of factors influencing optimization of aquaponic system

A. Optimizing aquaculture setup

Economically important fishes are frequently used in aquaponic systems. *Oreochromis niloticus* Linnaeus, 1758 (Nile tilapia) is considered one of the most commonly farmed aquaculture species due to its fast growth, high adaptability, easy maintenance, and good market demand. Diametrical growth of both species suggests multiple fish species use or polyponics (polyculture + aquaponics). Less oxygen use of *Cyprinus carpio* Linnaeus, 1758 (Common carp) comparison with Tilapia extended the stable performance of the coupled aquaponics. *Scortum barcoo* McCulloch & Waite, 1917 (Jade perch) is another potential candidate recently in interest owing to its profitability, adaptability, palatability and accelerated growth rate coupled with high feed conversion ratio. Aquaponic vegetables showed best plant growth combining of Nile tilapia with *Solanum lycopersicum* Linnaeus, 1753 (tomato). *Cucumis sativus* L., (1753) (Cucumber) fresh biomass tended to have a higher yield in combination with Common carp [23]. Optimizing the stocking density for the desired fish species is the key to a successful aquaponic

system. This is dependent upon the stocking of plants in the system owing to its absorptive capacity to purify water during recirculation. A recent study demonstrated ideal fish to plant ratio to be of 1: 1.3 for integrating Nile tilapia and *Spinacia oleracea* L., (1753) (Spinach) in inland saline groundwater. This ratio gave best yield with maximum nitrate, phosphate and potassium removal efficiency from the effluent [24]. In a trial conducted by Al-Zahrani et al. (2023), average final body weight, specific growth rate, weight gain and survival rate of Nile tilapia coupled with spinach was significantly higher in the 3 kg.m⁻³ treatment. Yield of spinach increased as the stocking density increased ($P < 0.05$) but growth rate was lowered, henceforth, suggesting a range of stocking up to 6 kg.m⁻³. Rayhan et al. (2018) found that the average weight gain, specific growth percent per day, survival rate and final length significantly increased when stocked with 30 tilapia per tank but the highest fish yield and plant biomass was shown by tank with 50 tilapias.

Fishes of more than 100 g of body mass are fed at 1 % of body weight per day as per the current recommended feeding guideline. The feeding rate ratio is 40 – 50 g. m⁻² for leafy greens; and 50 – 80 g. m⁻² for fruiting vegetables and gradually increased by 1 - 2% body weight per day [25] choice of feeding and fasting schedules plays a significant role in system efficiency and overall productivity. Increasing feeding frequency favour water quality (Liang and Chien, 2013). Results of experiment conducted in Nile Tilapia in an NFT-based aquaponic system suggests that three-day feeding followed by one-day fasting regime results in efficient nutrient utilization, higher productivity, and profitability and marketable biomass of spinach. Though this regime showed lesser yield efficiency than daily feeding regime, but was not statistically significant [27]. A uniform feeding regime significantly enhanced crop quality and 30 % nitrogen use efficiency compared to increasing feeding regime and hydroponic systems. It also improved water quality by reducing harmful compounds like nitrite (NO₂ – N) and sodium (Na) while increasing early availability of essential nutrients (NO₃ – N, PO₄–P, Ca, Mg), supporting better seedling establishment, higher photosynthetic rates, chlorophyll content, and total leaf nitrogen throughout the production period [28]. Nitrogen species in aquaponic systems are transformed into various forms primarily via biochemical processes. The major factors affecting nitrogen transformations are pH, dissolved oxygen, hydraulic loading rate, ammonia and nitrite concentration, and C:N ratio [29]. Fish feed being the only input to the system determines the quality and amount of irrigation water that fertilizes the plants. Fishmeal serves as a primary protein source in commercial aquafeeds, particularly for carnivorous and omnivorous fish species. Feed is another major factor that contributes to cost for about 40 – 60 % of the total production cost [30,31]. Recently, commercial feed formulations using alternative plant or animal by products is on trend [32–36]

B. Optimizing filtration setup

Filtration system bridges between aquaculture and hydroponic systems. It consists of mechanical and biological filtration units. Mechanical filtration involves removal of solid debris while passing all dissolved nutrients towards biological filtration unit. This is where beneficiary bacteria nitrify the ammonia. Nutrient rich water leaves the filter and gets delivered to roots, serving as fertilizer. In media-based culture systems, media bed itself harbours beneficiary bacteria. Filter screens out solid wastes. Parabolic screen filter (PSF) or a cylindro - conical clarifier can be used. PSF used an experiment performed less effectively in removing total suspended solids compared to the clarifier, and require more labour to clean [37] Thus, it is considered unsuitable for application in a larger raft aquaponic system. Beneficiary bacteria are nitrifying bacteria *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrobacter* that converts ammonia in fish excreta into nitrites and nitrates that can be absorbed by plants for their nutritional requirements. Another important group of bacteria reported in aquaponics is *Pseudomonas* spp. which has assortment of iron acquisition and regulatory genes hence stimulates plant growth [38]. They function as a biocontrol agent controlling plant diseases by depriving the pathogen from iron nutrition, showing antagonistic and antifungal activity in response to *Fusarium graminearum* and preventing root rot [39]. *Bacillus* spp. can be used to increase phosphorus availability and as a plant growth promoter [40].

C. Optimizing hydroponic setup

Plants require 14 mineral elements to fulfil adequate nutrition (Marschner, 2012; Wege et al., 2017). This includes macronutrients like nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), sulphur (S), and chlorine (Cl) and the micronutrients like boron (B), iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), nickel (Ni), and molybdenum (Mo). Suboptimal levels of any of these causes deficiency symptoms whereas excessive levels may cause toxicity. Hence optimizing mineral nutrition is an important factor in crop production. Dissolved nitrogen is supplied adequately for most plant species if given high stocking density and feed rations per volume of water exchange [41], eliminating the need for additional nitrogen fertilization. Significantly higher levels of NO₂-N and Na are reported in aquaponics compared to hydroponics, which could be a reason to limit plant growth and yield in aquaponics [42]. Macronutrients such as P, K, Ca, Mg, S and micronutrients such as Fe often accumulate insufficiently in dissolved form in the recirculating aquaponic system (RAS) process water, needing for external supplementation in a plant-centric system [12,16,43–47]. Additionally, chemical inputs may also be required to counteract disease and other plant stressors. A recent study conducted on water spinach revealed increased photoperiod favour water quality. 24 h light resulted in 2.4 % higher fish growth, 12 % higher plant growth and lower accumulation of all nitrogen and phosphate in water [48]. Media-based systems use different growth substrates like gravel, pumice, charcoal etc. Studies showed pumice substrate having better performance than mixture of pumice-charcoal substrate in percentage nutrients reduction. Charcoal substrate showed highest reduction efficiency for phosphates. Spinach performed better under mixture of pumice and charcoal treatment. They suggested nutrient reduction efficiency can be increased by replicating the hydroponic units with appropriate substrate to increase retention time of water in hydroponics

for increased fish and crops production. Recommended planting density of Indian Spinach coupled with *Nile Tilapia* in RAS is 12 plants.m⁻² combined with 45 fish per tank. The highest weight gain, percent weight gain, specific growth rate and protein efficiency ratio of fish was obtained at this density but showed lowest feed conversion ratio. Plants in this density showed highest per plant number of leaves, length, weight and yield compared to 4, 8, 16 plants.m⁻² [49].

D. Optimizing water usage and quality

Daily water requirement accounted for < 2 % of total volume used in aquaponic systems proves its water usage efficiency. Additionally integrating fish to plant ratio 1:1.3 had daily water requirement of 1.16 – 1.29 % which was found to be significantly lower than any other stocking ratios [24]. Another experiment done for four weeks used only 3.3 % water with that consumed for fish production to be just 20.0 L.kg⁻¹ [48]. Control of water quality is essential for the ideal growing conditions for both species in aquaponics [50,51]. Water environment which is suboptimal for plant growth, makes them less productive and profitable compared to those grown in hydroponics [31,42]. Actively growing plants can act as a biological filter and improve water quality by removing nutrients from aquaponic solution, and this, in turn, contributes to maintaining fish health and wellbeing [20].

Parameters such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), temperature (T), and dissolved oxygen (DO) are to be maintained at optimal levels for plant, fish and bacteria to achieve maximum growth rates and yield [16,51]. The implementation of fertilizers up to the ideal electrical conductivity for plants carries the risk of acute or chronic toxicity for fish [12]. pH within the range of 6.5 – 7.5 is usually maintained in aquaponic systems [52]. Maintaining pH values at a neutral level can lead to plant nutrient deficiencies or high toxicity of ammonia to fish. Higher range of pH, typically more than the optimal range of 5.5 – 6.5 in hydroponics can contribute to leaf chlorosis or yellowing. Such was observed in lettuce, basil, cherry tomato [42], tomato [53] and eggplant [54]. pH also affects the availability and stability of Fe chelates (Somerville et al., 2014; Zou et al., 2016; Wongkiew et al., 2017), controls fish metabolism, ammonia and heavy metal toxicity to fish. In addition, pH is an important factor influencing denitrification, microbial oxidation of ammonium to nitrite and nitrate. Zou [55] reported that nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions in aquaponic systems decreased as the pH was increased to 9.0, indicating that a low pH (6.0) significantly inhibited ammonia oxidising bacteria. It is therefore crucial to stabilise pH in the aquaponic system since it is critical to all three organisms within a recirculating system, *i.e.*, fish, plants and microbes [20]. Nitrifying bacteria function adequately within a pH range of 6.0 – 8.5 [25]. The ideal pH range for nitrifying bacteria is between 7.0 and 8.3 [56], the ideal pH range for nitrifying bacteria was between 7.0 and 8.3, but their growth was limited below a pH of 6.5, with an ideal pH of 7.8 [52]. Depending on the species, plants may tolerate a pH of between 5.0 and 7.0. For optimal growth of both fish and plant crops, the pH must be maintained between 6.5 and 8 [57].

Nile tilapia reared at salinities 9, 6 and 3 g. L⁻¹ showed significantly higher feed efficiency ratio and protein efficiency ratio compared to freshwater. The feed conversion ratio ranged between 1.31 – 1.43 and survival of 100 % with statistically similar final mean biomass. Second spinach harvest showed highest yield in 9 g. L⁻¹. Based on the overall production performance, water quality parameters, a salinity of 9 g.L⁻¹ was found to be the best for the integration of Nile tilapia and Spinach in an aquaponic system [58]. Ideal temperature range for tilapia growth is between 27 and 29 °C. Nitrification occur between 7 and 35 °C [59], with an ideal temperature of 15 - 25 °C, and that the best temperature for nitrifying bacteria is 25 - 30 °C. Enduta [60] showed total NH₃-N and total nitrite-N removal ranging from 78.32 to 85.48 and 82.93 to 92.22 %, respectively, utilizing water spinach in aquaponics system, and Astuti [61] presented the nitrite removal efficiency of water spinach was 88.15 % in aquaponics system.

III. NUTRIENT SUPPLEMENTATION: NECESSITY

Nutrition in aquaponics systems are predominantly from the waste excreted by fishes. These aquacultural effluents has dissolved or suspended solids rich in nitrogen and phosphorus produced from fish excretion via the gills, faeces and leftover feed [22,29,62,63]. As the aquaculture effluent flows into the hydroponic component, nutrients are filtered and transformed by nitrification and mineralisation processes. These contain macronutrients and micronutrients essential for plant growth. Nitrogen from ammonia are majorly 80 – 90 % may be excreted by fish via the gills is a readily available nitrogen source for plants [29]. The closed-loop, coupled aquaponics system has certain limitations that prevent it from being equally or more productive compared to conventional cultivation systems such as hydroponics [64–66]. Despite the differences in requirement of nutrient concentrations by different plants, most of the nutrient availability in aquaponic systems are driven by factors such as fish species, growth stage, stocking density, feeding rate and feed composition, and the rate of microbial nitrification [20,52].

One key challenges in conventional aquaponics is the difference in the nutrient requirements between the two components, aquaculture and hydroponics [3,44]. Although nitrified effluent contain macronutrients and micronutrients required for plant growth, since the sole nutrient source in the system is fish feed which in turn are mostly limited in Ca, K, and Fe, results in nutrient deficiencies and suboptimal productivity of plants. [62,65,67]. Aquaponic system also faces the problem of nutrients deficiency, including iron [68–71], potassium [72–75], magnesium [76]. Suboptimal levels of calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and/or nitrate (NO₃ – N) from ingested fish feed is considered as one of the major contributors to leaf yellowing and low yield as plants require these macronutrients in large quantity [42]. Nevertheless, plants do thrive in solutions that have lower nutrient levels than standard hydroponic solutions. This is true for green leafy vegetables that rarely need additional nutritional supplementation [65]. Hydroponic researches reveal that conventional nutrient solutions typically contain high macronutrient concentrations (over 10 mM), which saturate the secondary

nutrient uptake system [77–79]. However, such levels are not required in early plant growth stages when demand is less [80]. In contrast, closed-circulation systems like aquaponics rely on nutrient sources from digested fish effluent, resulting in lower nutrient concentrations [65]. While suitable for leafy crops like *Lactuca sativa* L., (1753) (lettuce) [81,82] these lower levels can limit yields in fruiting crops like tomatoes [4]. Still, tomato yields under organic fertilization were comparable to mineral systems in soil and short-term hydroponics [83,84]. But in an economic point of view, feed manipulation and supplementation can give promising results in aquaponics. Hence there is a requirement to supplement the system with deficit nutrients in order to achieve maximised production.

Delaide [81] found that, RAS water supplemented with high-purity mineral salts to match the nutrient concentrations of the hydroponic control showed a significant 39 % increase in shoot mass of lettuce coupled with tilapia. But another study showed no change in growth performance of Jade perch when minerals supplemented using a hydroponics commercial blend fertilizer at 10 % of the dosage coupled with lettuce [85]. Additionally, chemical inputs will be needed to counterbalance stresses like disease and others [86] which in turn contribute to long-term operational expenses [5]. Hence, despite the benefits of integrated systems, high capital expenses during system construction. Another challenge in the commercial fish feed is in its protein source, the fishmeal [30]. Its drawbacks include high price, limited availability, variable quality, environmental degradation, and ethical concerns [87]. It is in this scenario, manipulation of nutrient composition of aquaculture feeds comes into picture. Had been proposed a long time ago as a strategy to modulate nutrient balance and potentially eliminate the necessity for nutrient supplementation in water [88]. This approach which did not receive wide interest then, has recently caught the attention of the scientific community. In theory, adjusting fish diet nutrients to match plant needs could create an ideal balance, sustaining optimal nutrient levels without extra supplementation in the water [89].

IV. METHODS OF NUTRIENT APPLICATIONS INTO THE SYSTEM

Despite the advantages of conventional aquaponics, a key challenge is that plant species have varying nutrient and mineral requirements, that may often not in the ideal balance by the aquaculture wastes [90,91]. Nutrients can be applied in aquaponic system in a number of ways as depicted in figure 2. Supplementation can be directly to the fish or plant species or indirectly to aquaponic water sources [72,73,81]. Some others have demonstrated foliar application of potassium to alleviate nutrient deficiency in leafy and root vegetables in aquaponics [53,75]. Since the absorption of nutrients by plants is dependent on root absorption rather than through pore and water stoma of leaf, the addition of nutrients directly into water or fertigation might be more efficient, and impact of the nutrient addition into the culture water on the fish and microbes is a complex phenomenon yet to be addressed in aquaponics [92]. Recently direct supplementation or manipulation of fish feeds has gained more importance [89,93]. Table 2 depicts the recent researches on different nutrients supplemented into the system through various methods.

Figure 2. Overview of methods of nutrient supplementation in aquaponic system

A. Aquaculture Supplementations

a) In fish tank:

Luo [69] examined various concentrations of chelated iron supplementations (1, 2, 3, 4 mg.L⁻¹) in mirror carp-lettuce based media bed aquaponics. 1 mg. L⁻¹ iron treatment resulted in the highest weight gain, increased muscle crude fat, muscle iron content, higher catalase activity, lower malondialdehyde levels in fish indicating reduced oxidative stress, but gave lowest feed conversion ratio. For lettuce, the 2 mg. L⁻¹ treatment produced the highest chlorophyll, increased yield, highest nitrogen utilization with no negative effects on water quality concluding 1 – 2 mg. L⁻¹ of glycine chelated iron in every 20 days to improve fish and vegetable growth and nitrogen efficiency in aquaponic systems.

b) *In aquaculture wastewater:*

Tsoumalakou (Tsoumalakou et al., 2023) identified Fe deficiency as the major bottleneck in spinach cultivation in closed-loop aquaponics systems, with Fe supplementation significantly improving spinach function and yield. Fe-treated plants outperformed Fe + K - treated plants in chlorophyll content, photosynthetic rates, and photochemical efficiency, primarily due to higher quantum yield of electron transport but no variation in growth and functional performance was observed. Untreated plants showed a coordinated down-regulation in light absorption, photochemistry, and carboxylation, leading to early chlorophyll loss and potential structural defects in the photosynthetic machinery. They recommended application of Fe-EDDHA (Ethylenediamine di-2-hydroxyphenyl acetate ferric) or Fe-HBED (N, N'-bis (2-hydroxyphenyl) ethylenediamine- N, N'- diacetic acid) chelates above pH 6.5. Another study on *Pangasianodon hypophthalmus* (Sauvage, 1878) (Striped catfish) - spinach nutrient film technique (NFT) - based aquaponic system revealed iron dose of 1.5 mg. L⁻¹ optimal for plant growth and fish health. Iron supplementation positively affected uptake of essential macronutrients and micronutrients. 2.5 mg. L⁻¹ showed highest yield, fish body weight. However, higher doses of iron (2.0 mg. L⁻¹, 2.5 mg. L⁻¹) decreased the dry weight of spinach leaves, indicating that excessive iron may be harmful to plants. It also increased plasma cortisol and glucose in fish, indicating stress. Thus, Fe supplementation at 1.5 mg. L⁻¹ per fortnight was recommended to enhance plant growth, net yield, and their nutrient uptake in aquaponics systems [68]. Choi [95] examined the effects of nutritional supplements on aquaponic water and plant growth, using KHCO₃, KHCO₃ + Fe-EDTA, and KHCO₃ + Fe-EDTA + KH₂PO₄ treatments for geranium and goldfish. They suggested KHCO₃ + Fe-EDTA treatment exhibited the highest height, number of leaves, significantly better leaf length, width, normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), soil plant analysis development (SPAD) values with no leaf discoloration. Potassium, phosphate, and sulphate levels were notably higher in KHCO₃ + Fe-EDTA + KH₂PO₄ treatment. Several researchers have supplemented potassium in aquaponics cultivating spinach [73]. Tomato [53]. Lettuce, Mint, Mushroom Herb [96], Okra [74], rocket plant [97], Coriander, Parsley, Mint, and Radish [46]. Harika [72] evaluated the effects of potassium supplementation on Basil coupled with Pangasius in four dosages—90, 120, 150 and 180 mg. L⁻¹. Higher yield with improved height, dry weight, leaf length and width with enhanced uptake of phosphorus, nitrogen, sulphur, potassium, copper, iron, zinc, and manganese were observed in all higher dosages. But for fish, 180 mg. L⁻¹ resulted in lower fish body weight and significantly higher serum cortisol and glucose levels thus recommended a potassium dose of 150 mg. L⁻¹ as optimal for *Ocimum basilicum* L., (1753) (basil) - pangasius aquaponics.

c) *In fish feed:*

Luo [98] explored various dietary iron sources with ferrous sulfate, ferrous citrate and ferrous glycinate on juvenile mirror carp and lettuce in aquaponic system and found increased weight gain and nitrogen utilization of fish in citrate and glycinate treatments and suggested citrate treatment for increased weight gain, muscle, whole body iron, blood hematocrit, and nitrogen utilization. In a similar study conducted by Liu [99] in mirror carp coupled with tomato and pak choi, significantly improved plant growth parameters such as plant height, diameter of stem, leaf count, and fruit yield were observed in iron levels 200 – 400 mg. kg⁻¹. In fish, 800 mg. kg⁻¹ had initial physiological benefits but significantly reduced growth and feed conversion efficiency. Dicalcium phosphate is a common phosphorus supplement. Potassium phosphate is one substitute which primarily provides phosphorus, can also contribute to potassium input. Duarte and Cerozi [100] replaced dicalcium phosphate with increasing amounts of potassium phosphate (control: 100 % dicalcium phosphate and calcium carbonate and 0% potassium phosphate and calcium chloride; 50 % treatment : 50 % dicalcium phosphate, and calcium carbonate and 50% potassium phosphate and calcium chloride; and 100 % treatment : 0 % dicalcium phosphate and calcium carbonate, and 100 % potassium phosphate and calcium chloride) and found that supplementing potassium in fish feeds via potassium phosphate up to 3.85 % inclusion in the feed formulation optimized plant growth without compromising fish health or growth. Haematological parameters had no significant difference among fish, but weight gain was enhanced. Plants in systems with supplemented feeds showed improved growth, with higher potassium concentrations increasing nutrient availability and supporting plant development. Direct addition of potassium to aquaponic water and supplementation in aquaponic nutrient solutions did not affect *Pangasius* and *Tilapia* performance [72, 73,97]. These studies refers that potassium supplementation led to greater plant biomass. Siqwepu [89] reported no significant increase in water potassium levels with supplemented diets, and plant growth was not evaluated in that study, which focused on recirculating aquaculture systems with only fish. A previous research revealed fishes excrete approximately 92 % of ingested potassium into the water within 24 h of feeding [100], with potassium levels outside their requirements not significantly affecting fish development.

Fruit waste, is an inexpensive or zero-cost by-product of agro-industrial processes which can reduce dependence on expensive conventional fish feed ingredients. Table 1 summarizes recent researches and suggestions on aquafeed incorporated fruit wastes. Studies show that incorporating fruit waste into fish feed can lower feed costs by improving feed conversion ratios and reducing overall production expenses, while maintaining or even enhancing the nutritional value of the feed, particularly in terms of fibre, vitamins, and antioxidants [101]. The cost-effectiveness of utilizing these by-products, alongside their positive environmental impact by reducing food waste, suggests that incorporating fruit waste in aquaculture feed is a viable and profitable strategy [102]. Fish fed fruit-waste-based diets also exhibited enhanced resistance to *Aeromonas hydrophila*, improved haematological profiles, and lower stress markers in blood serum, suggesting an immunostimulatory effect. Incorporating fruit waste as an additive in feed in bio-floc systems generally has no reported negative impact on water quality or the carbon-to-nitrogen ratio [103]. A carbon-to-nitrogen ratio of 10 – 15 is typically required to stimulate heterotrophic bacterial growth, that can convert nitrogenous waste to microbial biomass (Nisar et al.,2022). Inclusion of rambutan seed in Tilapia diets did not negatively affect water quality [105]. Salem and Abdel-Ghany [106] fed Nile Tilapia fingerlings with orange peel-based diets. Their findings suggested an optimum level of 2 g kg⁻¹ diet can act as a growth promoter and improve the nutrient absorptive ability of the intestine for Nile tilapia fingerlings which showed best weight gain (WG), final weight (FW), specific growth rate (SGR) and feed conversion ratio (FCR). Height of villi of the anterior intestine progressively increased as the supplementation level increased in the diets. Graph 1 provides a comparative analysis of SGR of tilapia fed with different fruit waste based diets Experiment on gilthead sea bream by Salem [137] also revealed increased growth performance of fish and feed utilization as the concentration of the additive was raised (up to 5 g. kg⁻¹ diet) and increased crude protein while decreasing lipids and harmful gut bacteria. Tonsy [108] supplemented digestrom (200 mg. kg⁻¹ diet) along with varied levels of orange peel waste (0 %, 50 %, and 75 %) as a partial replacement for yellow corn for *Oreochromis mossambicus* (Peters, 1852) (Mozambique tilapia). The best results regarding weight gain and nutritional content were observed in diet containing 50 % orange peel waste. This level when paired with 30% protein diet, showed increment in dry matter and ash content, and reduction in body fat. But 50 % of corn replacement in a 25 % protein diet led to higher body protein and fat. Increasing orange peel inclusion to 75 % negatively affected physiological responses leading to notable increase in red blood cell count, urea, and triglyceride levels, while reducing the concentrations of all studied hormones, indicating potential stress or metabolic imbalance at this high substitution level suggesting 50 % replacement level. Lee [109] evaluated the effects of blood orange peel as dietary additive on the growth, body composition, and health of juvenile black rockfish and suggested 10 g. kg⁻¹ giving highest specific growth rate, final weight, weight gain, protein efficiency ratio and retention, antioxidant enzyme activity, superior nutritional profiles. In a similar experiment, Gressler [110] found improved final weight and weight gain among all treatments groups when fed Nile tilapia with Bitter orange peel powder (BOPP) Even though lower dosages had reduced crude protein at 10 g. kg⁻¹ enhanced intestinal villi development and showed increased nuclear and cytoplasmic areas in tissue The 40 g. kg⁻¹ group exhibited increased total lipids, triglycerides, and cholesterol levels. Another study revealed sweet orange peel powder improved growth and feed efficiency in Nile tilapia over 60 and 98 days, particularly when used in combination with peel oil [106]. Diet containing essential oil (EO) extracted from bitter orange also enhanced growth efficiency (final weight, relative and specific growth rates, and feed conversion ratio), and gene expression in common carp and silver catfish a low-dose supplementation (0.25 %) [111,112]. Similarly, Mozambique tilapia showed improved growth and reduced glucose and cholesterol levels with orange EO [113]. *Labeo catla* (Hamilton, 1822)(Catla) fed methanolic orange peel extract showed improved survival, growth, and nutrient profiles without adverse metabolic effects [114]. Ngugi [115] investigated the impact of bitter lemon peel EO on *Aeromonas hydrophila* challenged *Labeo victorianus* fingerlings at 1 %, 2 %, 5 %, and 8 % inclusion levels. Up to 5 % inclusion significantly improved disease resistance, plasma cortisol, triglycerides, total protein and albumin levels, plasma glucose, mean cell haemoglobin, mean cell haemoglobin concentration, neutrophil, red blood cell and white blood cell while decreased cholesterol levels showing enhanced immune responses thereby indicating higher levels of serum immunoglobulins, lysozyme activity, and respiratory burst activity with increasing EO concentrations. These results are in line with the phytochemical profile of orange peel to be rich in bioactive compounds like limonene, flavonoids, phenolics, coumarins, alkaloids, saponins, and pectin [112,116–122]. Limonene, a major constituent, has been associated with the upregulation of key genes involved in somatotrophic axis-mediated growth (insulin growth factor I), digestion of nutrients, absorption, transport (mucin-like protein and oligo-peptide transporter), lipid assimilation (lipoprotein lipase and alkaline phosphatase), and antioxidant catalase enzyme activity [123]. High phenolics, fibre and pectin content could be reasons for improved gut functioning. Experimental diets containing 2 % fruit wastes—citrus, and banana peel—resulted in significantly improved WG along with FCR in tilapia fingerlings, while fish length and survival rates showed no significant differences. Among the fruit wastes, 2 % banana peel led to better FCR and survival [124]. Diets combining multiple fruit wastes proved better health and growth than single-waste treatments showing synergistic effect. In specific trials conducted by Sulaiman [101] on hybrid red tilapia with jackfruit pulp (JP), pineapple skin (PS) and grated coconut (GC), PS and GC achieved highest final weights. Similarly, in Malaysian mahseer, body weight gains were significantly higher in those fed mixed JP + GC and JP alone. The FCR in mahseer was significantly reduced in all fruit-waste treatments, indicating more efficient feed utilization. Improved energy storage (whole body lipid) reported in GC, JP, and the JP + GC mix treatments. These results suggest a cost-effective, sustainable strategy for improving aquaculture productivity while reducing waste consumption. A comparison of specific growth rates (SGR) of tilapia fed with fruit-based diet is mentioned in figure 3.

Hough [125] evaluated linseed oil (LO) and sunflower oil (SO) supplementation as source of omega-3 fatty acid on tilapia physiology and immunology showing decreased blood glucose while increased plasma protein. Luo [93] assessed dietary nano selenium

supplementation to Koi carp, coupled with Lettuce and showed weight gain rate, carotenoid content in 0.6 and 1.2 mg. kg⁻¹ group to be significantly higher, but feed conversion ratio, malondialdehyde level, ammonia and nitrite were lower. 2.4 mg. kg⁻¹ group showed higher skin redness, serum globulin. Black soldier fly larvae (BSFL), the larval stage of *Hermetia illucens*, are non-pest insects capable of converting organic waste into high-quality biomass, making them a sustainable protein source for aquafeeds. BSFL meals, both full-fat (FF) and defatted (DF), have shown promise as partial or complete fishmeal substitutes in diets for various species including tilapia, trout, carp, catfish, and shrimp [126–131]. Another study assessed the effects of FF and DF BSFL meals, along with mineral supplementation, on tilapia-spinach aquaponic systems. Results showed that up to 30 % replacement with either FF or DF BSFL meal had no adverse effects on growth, feed utilization, survival, or body composition. Mineral supplementation further improved tilapia performance, suggesting it could help mitigate the limitations of high BSFL inclusion [132]. In a similar trial, Cummins [133] found most growth responses in Pacific white shrimp at inclusion rate less than 25 %. The effectiveness complete substitution with four protein sources (black soldier fly meal BSFM; poultry blood meal (PBM); and hydrolysed feather meal (HFM) was tested in *Colossoma macropomum* and *Clarias gariepinus* to explore the possibility to manipulate the nutrient efflux from RAS using alternative sustainable aquafeed components. The water from PBM and HFM-fed fish showed the highest efflux of total nitrogen while the efflux of soluble reactive phosphorus and calcium was highest in FM fed fish. BSFM-fed fish had the highest efflux of magnesium and regarding macronutrients, the species-specific effects were observed only in sulphur, with higher efflux from *C. macropomum*. Effluxes of other micronutrients showed diet- and species-specific effects, except for zinc and manganese, with similar effluxes between species [134]

Table 1: Researches on fruit waste supplementations and suggested results

Fruit	Supplementation in feed	Species (common name)	Result	Reference
Orange	Orange peel derived pectin	Nile Tilapia in biofloc	At 10 g kg ⁻¹ along with 10 ⁸ CFU g ⁻¹ <i>L. plantarum</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> significantly stimulated serum immune response, skin mucus, survival rate, growth performance, FCR 	[135]
	Orange peel	Nile tilapia	2 g kg ⁻¹ diets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> best WG, FW, SGR and FCR 	[106]
	Orange peel with digestrom (200 mg. kg ⁻¹) as replacing yellow corn in diet	Red tilapia	50% replacement level <ul style="list-style-type: none"> increased dry matter and ash content reduced body fat 	[108]
	Blood orange peel	Juvenile black rockfish	10 g. kg ⁻¹ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved growth performance, weight gain, specific growth rate, protein efficiency ratio, protein retention, lipid metabolism, digestive enzyme activity, antioxidant potential 	[109]
	Bitter orange peel powder	Nile tilapia	10 g. kg ⁻¹ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved FW, WG and villi development 	[110]
	Sweet orange peel powder with orange peel oil	Nile tilapia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improvements in gut function were attributed to the high phenolics, fibre and pectin content. 	[136]
	Orange peel	Gilthead sea bream	up to 5 g. kg ⁻¹ diet <ul style="list-style-type: none"> increased growth performance, feed utilization, crude protein decreasing lipids and harmful gut bacteria 	[137]

	Bitter orange EO	Common carp and silver catfish	low-dose (0.25 %)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> enhanced growth efficiency (FW, relative and specific growth rates, and FCR), and gene expression 	[111,112]
	Orange EO	Mozambique tilapia		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved growth reduced glucose, cholesterol levels 	[113]
	Orange EO	Rainbow trout		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lowered FCR increased protein efficiency 	-
	Methanolic orange peel extract	Catla		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved survival, growth, and nutrient profiles without adverse metabolic effects 	[114]
Pineapple	Pineapple peel powder	Nile Tilapia in bio-floc	At 10 g.kg ⁻¹ + 10 ⁸ CFU g ⁻¹ <i>L. plantarum</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved serum immune response, skin mucus, survival rate, growth performance, feed conversion ratio 	[138]
Rambutan	Rambutan seed	Nile tilapia in biofloc	10 g kg ⁻¹	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> improved growth performance, feed utilization, skin mucus, serum immunity Upregulation antioxidant related genes (IL1, IL8, LBP, GSTa, GPX, GSR) 	[105]
Mixture of fruits	pineapple skin (PS), pineapple crown (PC), jackfruit skin (JS), jackfruit pulp (JP), grated coconut (GC), mixed fruit wastes (JP + GC)	Hybrid red tilapia, Malaysian mahaseer		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All fruit-waste diets showed better growth, survival rates. Highest FW in JP and GC in tilapia, while JP + GC and JP in Mahaseer. Combined diet - better fish growth, immune response 	[101]
	Citrus and banana peel	Tilapia fingerlings	2 %	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improved FCR, WG 	[124]

Figure 3. Comparative specific growth rates (SGR) of tilapia fed with fruit- based diet. (O=orange: P= pineapple; J=jackfruit; C= coconut and B= banana)

B. Hydroponic Supplementations

a) Foliar spray:

Roosta and Hamidpour [22] compared the effects of foliar application of micro- and macro-nutrient on tomato in aquaponic and hydroponic system using 0.5 g.L⁻¹ at rate of 250 mL.plant⁻¹ with potassium sulphate (K₂SO₄), magnesium sulphate (MgSO₄ 7H₂O), ferrous (Fe)- ethylenediamine-N,N'-bis (EDDHA), manganese sulphate (MnSO₄ H₂O), boric acid (H₃BO₃), zinc chloride (ZnCl₂), and copper sulphate (CuSO₄ 5H₂O) and concluded that K, Mg, Fe, Mn, Zn, and Cu increased in concentrations in the leaves of aquaponic-treated plants. On the other hand, hydroponic-grown plants showed a significant increment of applied elements concentrations in the fruits indicating that foliar application of some elements can effectively alleviate nutrient deficiencies in the leaves of tomatoes grown on aquaponics. Bethe [139] observed compost tea sprayed water spinach yielded highest (5.56 kg), than molasses (4.73 kg) with tilapia production of 22.38 ton.ha⁻¹month⁻¹ at an FCR of 2.33 suggesting use of compost tea and molasses as

foliar spray to produce organic vegetables. Akter [140] applied Epsom salt to leaves at 5 % (in NFT) and roots at 373 kg.ha⁻¹ (in media bed) fortnightly. Root application showed the highest fish growth, specific growth rate but lowest FCR. Leaf application had the tallest plants indicating enhanced performance from Epsom salt applications with better water spinach production in NFT than media bed-based system. Afrin (Afrin et al., 2018) reported that the mean length and weight gain of tilapia was 9.04 ± 0.89 cm and 49.27 ± 9.79 g after 72 days in an aquaponics system with sea salt supplementation.

b) Fertigation/ directly to water / nutrient solution:

John [73] investigated the effects of potassium supplementation on spinach coupled with catfish in four dosages—90, 120, 150, and 180 mg. L⁻¹ out of which 180mg.L⁻¹ treatment showed significantly highest yield in second harvest followed by 150 mg.L⁻¹ with no significant differences in body weight but did improve nutrient content, particularly nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, iron, sulphur, and plasma glucose. They suggested that a potassium dose of 150 mg. L⁻¹ to be optimal. Research to study influence of different concentrations of organic waste extracts (Goat Manure Extract, GME; Banana Peel Extract, BPE) with treatments 0 % GME and BPE (control: irrigation water), 1 % GME, 2 % GME, 3 % GME, 3 % GME + 1 % BPE, 3 % GME + 2 % BPE on morphological and nutritional traits of loose-leaf Lettuce grown in hydroponic showed highest number of leaves, fresh weight, dry weight, carbohydrates, fat, fibre, calcium, phosphorus, sodium, potassium, chromium, thiamine, niacin, and energy under 3 + 2 treatment, whereas protein, ash, iron and riboflavin were greater under 3 + 1 except moisture contents. On contrary, Kechasov [143] reveal organic waste-based fertilizer decreases plant growth, development, and yield in hydroponics due to low concentration of essential minerals in the nutrient solution. It could increase fruit size, but not fruit quality and hence additional adjustment of nutrient supply is required to improve fruit quality. However, the nutrient content requires optimization by the selective addition of minerals or by the addition of a combination of different organic wastes for optimal plant development. This has several limitations, such as production of lower quality fruit, need for nitrification, and control of the nutrient composition of fertilizer. Pelayo Lind [144] explained this decreased biomass accumulation in organic waste-based treatment was due to presence of organic waste phytotoxins. For instance, Pak choi plants showed reduced biomass accumulation when cultivated in a closed hydroponic system with plant-derived digestate as a fertilizer.

c) Soil/ growing media

Zahan (Zahan et al., 2018) studied the effects of calcium supplementation in tomato-tilapia based aquaponics using chicken eggshell powder at 1 kg. decimal⁻¹ and 1.5 kg. decimal⁻¹ and showed highest daily fish growth rate, survival rate, superior tomato and fish yields in 1 kg. decimal⁻¹ suggesting its potential as calcium source to enhance productivity and reduce disease incidences (Iszhan et al., 2021). El-Serafy [146] worked counteract the heat accumulation in greenhouse which limit plant growth and quality using powders of banana, orange, and pomegranate peels, and their combinations, applied at 8 and 16 g. pot⁻¹ to Schefflera plants and found enhanced shoot and root growth, leaf pigments, relative water content, membrane stability index, and phenotypic plasticity index. They also increased phenol, flavonoid levels, and DPPH scavenging activity, alleviating oxidative stress by lowering H₂O₂ and malondialdehyde levels. Orange peel at 16 g. pot⁻¹ proved most effective, promoting root development and heat tolerance during early plant growth suggesting fruit peels as plant growth enhancers. Fruit peels from pomegranate, orange, and banana were also used among which pomegranate proved best for growth and yield without reported chlorosis. This improved soil fertility and could even induce shoot formation in *Vinca rosea* plant when added in tissue culture media highlighting the dual benefit of fruit peel extracts as both soil amendments and bio-based components. Jariwala and Syed, [147] used peel powders of citrus (orange, sweet lime, pomegranate) with acidic pH and alkaline (banana) with basic pH. Alkaline peel powder reduced soil acidity, while citric peel reduced salinity. Citric peel powder had higher nitrogen, while alkaline had more phosphorus and potassium. Islam [148] suggested banana peel biochar being potassium-rich, with 2 – 3% treatments improved plant vigour and biomass. Another study demonstrated that banana peel powder (BPP) - based bioformulation significantly enhanced rice growth, with treated plants showing the highest shoot length proving its potential as an effective organic carrier for biofertilizer development (Raj, Preethy and Rex, 2021). Leaf area increased with pulp extract and peel powder. While stem diameter was less affected, 10 ml L⁻¹ extract with 20 g. plant⁻¹ powder yielded the highest. Application of 3 g pineapple peel powder significantly improved water spinach growth, resulting in a maximum plant height and number of leaves. Additionally, incorporating ground banana and orange peels increased soil nitrogen content by 16 – 31 % and potassium by 12 – 24 % compared to conventional compost treatments highlighting the potential of specific fruit peels, particularly banana and pineapple, as nutrient-rich organic amendments to enhance plant growth and soil fertility. Thepsilvisut [149] explored the reuse of agro-industrial waste, particularly fruit peels like banana and orange, as partial substitutes for mineral fertilizers to reduce reliance on peat moss in producing sunflower and water spinach microgreens using growing media: peat moss (control), coconut coir dust (CD), leaf compost (LC), food waste compost (FC), and their combinations in 1:1 or 1:1:1 ratios. The highest sunflower microgreen yield (10,114.81 g m⁻²) was achieved using CD:LC (1:1 v/v), while water spinach performed best in CD, control, CD:LC (1:1), and CD:LC:FC (1:1:1) media, yielding 10,966.67–9800.00 g. m⁻² out of which CD and CD:LC proved the most effective media.

Table 2 Overview of different nutrients supplemented in aquaponic system

Nutrient supplement	Form of nutrient supplementation	Method of supplementation	Species (common name)	Recommendation	Reference
SINGLE NUTRIENT					
Fe	Ferrous glycinate	Fish tank	Mirror carp - Lettuce	1–2 mg. L ⁻¹	[69]
	Fe-EDDHA (6 %)	Aquaculture wastewater	Pangasius-Spinach	1.5 mg. L ⁻¹	[68]
	ferrous sulfate, ferrous citrate, ferrous glycinate (120 mg.kg ⁻¹)	Feed	Common carp-Lettuce	Ferrous citrate	[98]
	Ferric EDTA	Feed	Mirror carp-tomato	200 mg. kg ⁻¹	[99]
K	K ₂ SO ₄	Fertigation	Catfish-Spinach	150 mg. L ⁻¹	[73]
	---	Fertigation	Catfish-basil	150 mg. L ⁻¹	[72]
P	Phytase 1000 FTU kg ⁻¹	Feed	Tilapia-Lettuce	Need for extra K	[62]
	Dicalcium phosphate		Red Tilapia-lettuce	3.85 % inclusion	[100]
Se	Nano-Se. Kg ⁻¹	Feed	Koi Carp-Lettuce	1.55–1.57 mg. kg ⁻¹	[93]
Ca	calcium carbonate (chicken eggshell powder)	growing bed	Tilapia-Tomato	1 kg. decimal ⁻¹	[145]
MIXTURE OF NUTRIENTS					
Fe and K	Fe and Fe-K (Fe-DTPA - 11 % and K ₂ SO ₄)	Aquaponic water	Red tilapia-Spinach	Only Fe	[94]
Fe, K and P	KHCO ₃ , Fe-EDTA and KH ₂ PO ₄	Aquaponic water	Goldfish-Geranium	KHCO ₃ + Fe-EDTA	[95]
-	250 mL plant ⁻¹ with 0.5 g L ⁻¹ of K ₂ SO ₄ , MgSO ₄ 7H ₂ O, Fe-EDDHA, MnSO ₄ H ₂ O, H ₃ BO ₃ , ZnCl ₂ , CuSO ₄ 5H ₂ O	Foliar spray	-	Significant increase in aquaponic leaves and hydroponic fruit	[22]
OTHER THAN NUTRIENTS					
Mg, S	Magnesium sulphate (Epsom salt)	Foliar spray and root application (Media bed)	Tilapia-Water spinach	Foliar is better	[140]
Protein	BSFL meal	feed	Tilapia-Spinach	30 % replacement along with mineral addition	[132]
-----	Compost tea, Molasses	Foliar spray	Tilapia-Water Spinach	compost tea	[139]
Synbiotic	10 ⁸ CFU. ml ⁻¹	feed	Common carp-lettuce	Positive effect	[150]

V. CONCLUSION

The benefits of aquaponics extend beyond the simultaneous production of plants and fish, improved water use efficiency, reduced aquaculture waste release, reduced land footprint compared to traditional agriculture and inland aquaculture systems and much more. Aquaponics can be implemented in areas with limited arable land, enabling the production of fresh food closer to consumers [151]. This proximity shortens supply chains, reduces transportation emissions and enhances food security. However, various technological, economic and regulatory challenges hampers the widespread adoption of aquaponics [4,16,152]. Firstly, efficiently managing water quality is a challenge. Secondly, increase in feed cost do not cater to optimal plant requirements as the commercial aquaculture feeds are formulated to meet fish nutritional requirements and not of plants, leading to deficiency symptoms arising from suboptimal dissolved nutrient profiles in the RAS process water with regard to the concentrations and ratios [44,45]. Hence, the possibility of aquaponics lies in efficiency of optimization. Nutrient optimization is a major bottleneck of the system which can be achieved through external supplementation directly or indirectly. Manipulation of fish feeds for nutrient supplementations is the current trend. Inclusion of orange extracts in fish feed has been extensively studied. Researchers focus on this thrust area to enhance efficiency and sustainability.

VI. FUTURE PROSPECTS

In the direction to enhance efficiency and sustainability of aquaponic and aquaculture systems, several areas warrant further research. Research should also focus on improving the quality of fruit wastes used as feed additives by reducing their antinutritional factors and examining their effects on fish flesh and carcass quality. Additionally, it is crucial to assess the suitability and nutritional value of various fruit wastes for fish feed, as well as their effectiveness as carbon sources in bio-floc systems. Broader evaluations should consider the use of fruit waste in other species, the impact of lower inclusion levels, and specific physiological indicators such as immunological status to validate their role as aquafeed supplements. In hydroponic agriculture, further research is recommended on the use of goat manure and banana peel extracts for leafy vegetables like spinach, along with the development and application of other animal and fruit waste inputs. Optimizing the dose of Epsom salt in both NFT (Nutrient Film Technique) and media bed aquaponics systems remains essential, requiring more in-depth investigation. Similarly, studies involving a longer culture period (3 – 4 months) using 0.15 g of tilapia are recommended to evaluate the long-term impacts. Although iron supplementation in aquaponics may address iron deficiencies, it is important to examine its potential to increase bacterial fish pathogens. Despite existing reports suggesting pathogen levels remain non-threatening [38], future studies should clarify the interactions between iron addition and fish welfare.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Surya T C (lead) - conceptualization, methodology, writing original draft

Dr. Manjesh M - validation, supervision,

Megha Jeyan (supporting) – writing- editing and reviewing

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no that they have no conflict of interest.

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